

SOME CONGRUENCES FOR REGULAR PARTITIONS WITH DISTINCT ODD PARTS

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Abstract

Let $\text{pod}_\ell(n)$ denote the number of ℓ -regular partitions of a positive integer n into distinct odd parts. In this article, we find some congruences for $\text{pod}_5(n)$, $\text{pod}_7(n)$, $\text{pod}_9(n)$ and $\text{pod}_{25}(n)$ by using the congruence properties of $t_4(n)$, $t_6(n)$, $t_8(n)$ and $t_{24}(n)$, respectively, where $t_k(n)$ is the number of representations of n as a sum of k triangular numbers.

1. Introduction

Throughout this article, we let $q = e^{2\pi iz}$ with $\text{Im } z > 0$. We also define the q -shifted factorials as

$$(a; q)_\infty := \prod_{n=0}^{\infty} (1 - aq^n).$$

A special case of $(a; q)_\infty$ is given by

$$f_k = (q^k; q^k)_\infty = \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{nk}), \quad \text{for any } k \geq 1.$$

Furthermore, let $t_k(n)$ denote the *number of representations* as the sum of k triangular numbers of a positive integer n . The corresponding generating function of $t_k(n)$ is given by

$$\psi^k(q) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} t_k(n)q^n.$$

A *partition* of a positive integer n is any nonincreasing sequence of positive integers whose sum is n . We say that a partition of n is ℓ -regular if none of its parts

are divisible by ℓ . Moreover, let $\text{pod}_\ell(n)$ denote the number of ℓ -regular partitions with distinct odd parts. The generating function of $\text{pod}_\ell(n)$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \text{pod}_\ell(n)q^n = \frac{\psi(-q^\ell)}{\psi(-q)}. \tag{1}$$

Recently, the arithmetic properties of $\text{pod}_\ell(n)$ have been widely studied. See, for example, [1]-[5]. In this article, by using the congruence properties of $t_4(n)$, $t_6(n)$, $t_8(n)$ and $t_{24}(n)$, we prove some congruence relations for $\text{pod}_5(n)$, $\text{pod}_7(n)$, $\text{pod}_9(n)$ and $\text{pod}_{25}(n)$, respectively.

2. Main Results

In order to obtain the main results, we first prove the following lemmas.

Lemma 1. *For any $k \geq 0$, let p be an odd prime. Then we have the following:*

(i) *if $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, then*

$$t_4\left(\frac{p^k - 1}{2}\right) \equiv t_8(p^k) \equiv k + 1 \pmod{3}; \tag{2}$$

(ii) *if $p \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, then*

$$t_4\left(\frac{p^{2k} - 1}{2}\right) \equiv t_8(p^{2k}) \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \tag{3}$$

and

$$t_4\left(\frac{p^{2k+1} - 1}{2}\right) \equiv t_8(p^{2k+1}) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}; \tag{4}$$

(iii) *if $p \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, then*

$$t_4\left(\frac{p^k - 1}{2}\right) \equiv t_8(p^k) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}. \tag{5}$$

Proof. We write

$$\sigma_t(p^k) = \sum_{i=0}^k (p^t)^i = \frac{(p^t)^{k+1} - 1}{p^t - 1}.$$

If t is odd, then for $p \equiv l \pmod{3}$ with $l = 0, 1, 2$, we have

$$p^t \equiv l \pmod{3}.$$

Consequently, we can deduce that

$$\sigma_t(p^k) \equiv k + 1 \pmod{3}, \quad p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}; \tag{6}$$

$$\sigma_t(p^{2k}) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, \quad \sigma_t(p^{2k+1}) \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, \quad p \equiv 2 \pmod{3}; \tag{7}$$

$$\sigma_t(p^k) \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, \quad p \equiv 0 \pmod{3}. \tag{8}$$

We make use of the following identity from [6]:

$$t_4(n) = \sigma_1(2n + 1), \tag{9}$$

where $\sigma_k(n) = \sum_{d|n} d^k$ is the standard divisor function. Replacing n by $(p^k - 1)/2$ in (9), we obtain

$$t_4\left(\frac{p^k - 1}{2}\right) = \sigma_1(p^k). \tag{10}$$

We also use the following identity from [6]:

$$t_8(n) = \sigma_3(n) - \sigma_3\left(\frac{n}{2}\right). \tag{11}$$

Similarly, replacing n by p^k in (11), we obtain

$$t_8(p^k) = \sigma_3(p^k). \tag{12}$$

Combining (6), (7), (8), (10) and (12), we deduce (2)-(5). □

The proof of the following lemma is similar to the the proof of Lemma 1, and we omit the proof.

Lemma 2. *For any $k \geq 0$, let p be an odd prime. Then we have the following:*

(i) *if $p \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$, then*

$$t_4\left(\frac{p^k - 1}{2}\right) \equiv k + 1 \pmod{5};$$

(ii) *if $p \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$, then*

$$t_4\left(\frac{p^{4k} - 1}{2}\right) \equiv 1 \pmod{5};$$

$$t_4\left(\frac{p^{4k+1} - 1}{2}\right) \equiv 3 \pmod{5};$$

$$t_4\left(\frac{p^{4k+2} - 1}{2}\right) \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$$

and

$$t_4\left(\frac{p^{4k+3} - 1}{2}\right) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}.$$

(iii) if $p \equiv 3 \pmod{5}$, then

$$t_4 \left(\frac{p^{4k} - 1}{2} \right) \equiv 1 \pmod{5};$$

$$t_4 \left(\frac{p^{4k+1} - 1}{2} \right) \equiv 4 \pmod{5};$$

$$t_4 \left(\frac{p^{4k+2} - 1}{2} \right) \equiv 3 \pmod{5}$$

and

$$t_4 \left(\frac{p^{4k+3} - 1}{2} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{5};$$

(iv) if $p \equiv 4 \pmod{5}$, then

$$t_4 \left(\frac{p^{2k} - 1}{2} \right) \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$$

and

$$t_4 \left(\frac{p^{2k+1} - 1}{2} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{5};$$

(v) if $p \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, then

$$t_4 \left(\frac{p^k - 1}{2} \right) \equiv 1 \pmod{5}.$$

Lemma 3. For any $k \geq 0$, let p be an odd prime. The following congruences hold:

(i) if $p \equiv 1 \pmod{7}$, then

$$t_6 \left(\frac{3(p^{2k} - 1)}{4} \right) \equiv 2k + 1 \pmod{7}; \tag{13}$$

(ii) if $p \equiv 2, 5 \pmod{7}$, then

$$t_6 \left(\frac{3(p^{6k} - 1)}{4} \right) \equiv 1 \pmod{7}; \tag{14}$$

$$t_6 \left(\frac{3(p^{6k+4} - 1)}{4} \right) \equiv 5 \pmod{7} \tag{15}$$

and

$$t_6 \left(\frac{3(p^{6k+2} - 1)}{4} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{7}; \tag{16}$$

(iii) if $p \equiv 3, 4, 6 \pmod{7}$, then

$$t_6 \left(\frac{3(p^{6k} - 1)}{4} \right) \equiv 1 \pmod{7}; \tag{17}$$

$$t_6 \left(\frac{3(p^{6k+4} - 1)}{4} \right) \equiv 3 \pmod{7} \tag{18}$$

and

$$t_6 \left(\frac{3(p^{6k+2} - 1)}{4} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{7}; \tag{19}$$

(iv) if $p \equiv 0 \pmod{7}$, then

$$t_6 \left(\frac{3(p^{2k} - 1)}{4} \right) \equiv 1 \pmod{7}. \tag{20}$$

Proof. We use the following identity for $t_6(n)$, which was proved in [6] using the theory of elliptic functions:

$$t_6(n) = \frac{1}{8} \left(\sum_{d|4n+3, d \equiv 3 \pmod{4}} d^2 - \sum_{d|4n+3, d \equiv 1 \pmod{4}} d^2 \right). \tag{21}$$

If p is an odd prime, then for $k \geq 0$, we have

$$p^{2k} \equiv 1 \pmod{4}.$$

Consequently, replacing n by $3(p^{2k} - 1)/4$ in (21), we can conclude that

$$t_6 \left(\frac{3(p^{2k} - 1)}{4} \right) = \sum_{i=1}^{2k} p^{2i} = \frac{p^{2(2k+1)} - 1}{p^2 - 1}. \tag{22}$$

Hence equation (22) gives the congruences (13)-(20). □

Lemma 4. For any $k \geq 0$, let p be an odd prime. Then we have the following:

(i) if $p \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$, then

$$t_{24}(5p^k - 3) \equiv k + 1 \pmod{5}; \tag{23}$$

(ii) if $p \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$, then

$$t_{24}(5p^{4k} - 3) \equiv 1 \pmod{5}; \tag{24}$$

$$t_{24}(5p^{4k+1} - 3) \equiv 4 \pmod{5}; \tag{25}$$

$$t_{24}(5p^{4k+2} - 3) \equiv 3 \pmod{5} \tag{26}$$

and

$$t_{24}(5p^{4k+3} - 3) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}; \tag{27}$$

(iii) if $p \equiv 3 \pmod{5}$, then

$$t_{24}(5p^{4k} - 3) \equiv 1 \pmod{5}; \tag{28}$$

$$t_{24}(5p^{4k+1} - 3) \equiv 3 \pmod{5}; \tag{29}$$

$$t_{24}(5p^{4k+2} - 3) \equiv 2 \pmod{5} \tag{30}$$

and

$$t_{24}(5p^{4k+3} - 3) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}; \tag{31}$$

(iv) if $p \equiv 4 \pmod{5}$, then

$$t_{24}(5p^{2k} - 3) \equiv 1 \pmod{5} \tag{32}$$

and

$$t_{24}(5p^{2k+1} - 3) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}; \tag{33}$$

(v) if $p \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, then

$$t_{24}(5p^k - 3) \equiv 1 \pmod{5}. \tag{34}$$

Proof. We also use the following identity for $t_{24}(n)$, which was proved in [6] using the theory of elliptic functions:

$$176896t_{24}(n - 3) = \sigma_{11}(n) - \sigma_{11}\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) - \tau(n) - 2072\tau\left(\frac{n}{2}\right), \tag{35}$$

where $\tau(n)$ is the Ramanujan tau function. Let p be an odd prime and $k \geq 0$. Replacing n by $5p^k$ in (35), we obtain

$$t_{24}(5p^k - 3) \equiv \sigma_{11}(5p^k) - \tau(5p^k) \pmod{5}. \tag{36}$$

We note that

$$\sigma_{11}(5p^k) = \sum_{i=0}^k p^{11i} + \sum_{j=0}^k 5p^{11j} \equiv \sum_{i=0}^k p^{11i} = \frac{p^{11(k+1)} - 1}{p^{11} - 1} \pmod{5}. \tag{37}$$

Using the fact that $\tau(5p^k) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, we have

$$t_{24}(5p^k - 3) \equiv \sigma_{11}(5p^k) \equiv \sum_{i=0}^k p^{11i} = \frac{p^{11(k+1)} - 1}{p^{11} - 1} \pmod{5}. \tag{38}$$

Similarly as in the preceding discussion, Equation (38) gives the congruences (23)-(34). □

We now state and prove our main results of this article.

Theorem 1. For any $k \geq 0$, let p be an odd prime. Then we have the following:

(i) if $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, then

$$\text{pod}_9(p^k - 1) \equiv \text{pod}_9(2p^k + 1) \equiv k + 1 \pmod{3}; \tag{39}$$

(ii) if $p \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, then

$$\text{pod}_9(p^{2k} - 1) \equiv \text{pod}_9(2p^{2k} + 1) \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \tag{40}$$

and

$$\text{pod}_9(p^{2k+1} - 1) \equiv \text{pod}_9(2p^{2k+1} + 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}; \tag{41}$$

(iii) if $p \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, then

$$\text{pod}_9(p^k - 1) \equiv \text{pod}_9(2p^k + 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}. \tag{42}$$

Proof. Setting $\ell = 9$ in (1), we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \text{pod}_9(n)q^n = \frac{\psi(-q^9)}{\psi(-q)}. \tag{43}$$

Replacing q by $-q$ in (43), we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \text{pod}_9(n)(-1)^n q^n = \frac{\psi(q^9)}{\psi(q)} = \frac{f_{18}^2}{f_9} \cdot \frac{f_1}{f_2^2} \equiv f_2^{16} \cdot \frac{f_1}{f_9} \pmod{3}. \tag{44}$$

We make use of the following identity from [7]:

$$\frac{f_1}{f_9} = \frac{f_2 f_{12}^3}{f_4 f_6 f_{18}^2} - q \frac{f_4 f_6 f_{36}^2}{f_{12} f_{18}^3}. \tag{45}$$

By substituting (45) in (44), we can rewrite (44) as

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \text{pod}_9(n)(-1)^n q^n \equiv f_2^{16} \left(\frac{f_2 f_{12}^3}{f_4 f_6 f_{18}^2} - q \frac{f_4 f_6 f_{36}^2}{f_{12} f_{18}^3} \right) \pmod{3}. \tag{46}$$

Extracting the terms involving q^{2n} in (46) and replacing q^2 by q , we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \text{pod}_9(2n)q^n \equiv \frac{f_2^{16} f_2 f_{12}^3}{f_4 f_6 f_{18}^2} \equiv \frac{f_2^8}{f_1^4} \pmod{3}.$$

Equating the coefficients of q^n , we find that

$$\text{pod}_9(2n) \equiv t_4(n) \pmod{3}. \tag{47}$$

Similarly, extracting the terms involving q^{2n+1} in (46), we obtain

$$-\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \text{pod}_9(2n+1)q^{2n+1} \equiv -q \frac{f_2^{16} f_4 f_6 f_{36}^2}{f_{12} f_{18}^3} \equiv -q \frac{f_4^{16}}{f_2^8} \pmod{3}. \tag{48}$$

Dividing (48) by $-q$ and replacing q^2 by q , we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \text{pod}_9(2n+1)q^n \equiv \frac{f_2^{16}}{f_1^8} \pmod{3}. \tag{49}$$

Equating the coefficients of q^n in (49), we find that

$$\text{pod}_9(2n+1) \equiv t_8(n) \pmod{3}. \tag{50}$$

Congruences (39)-(42) follows from (47), (50) and Lemma 1. $\square$

To prove the remaining theorems, we need to state the following congruence. If p is prime, then for $k \geq 0$, we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \text{pod}_{p^k}(n)(-1)^n q^n = \frac{\psi(q^{p^k})}{\psi(q)} \equiv \psi^{p^k-1}(q) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} t_{p^k-1}(n)q^n \pmod{p},$$

which implies

$$\text{pod}_{p^k}(n)(-1)^n \equiv t_{p^k-1}(n) \pmod{p}. \tag{51}$$

Combining (51) with Lemma 2, Lemma 3 and Lemma 4, we can derive the following theorems.

Theorem 2. *For any $k \geq 0$, let p be an odd prime. Then we have the following:*

(i) *if $p \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$, then*

$$\text{pod}_5\left(\frac{p^k-1}{2}\right) \equiv k+1 \pmod{5};$$

(ii) *if $p \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$, then*

$$\text{pod}_5\left(\frac{p^{4k}-1}{2}\right) \equiv 1 \pmod{5};$$

$$\text{pod}_5\left(\frac{p^{4k+1}-1}{2}\right) \equiv 3 \pmod{5};$$

$$\text{pod}_5\left(\frac{p^{4k+2}-1}{2}\right) \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$$

and

$$\text{pod}_5\left(\frac{p^{4k+3}-1}{2}\right) \equiv 0 \pmod{5};$$

(iii) if $p \equiv 3 \pmod{5}$, then

$$\text{pod}_5 \left(\frac{p^{4k} - 1}{2} \right) \equiv 1 \pmod{5};$$

$$\text{pod}_5 \left(\frac{p^{4k+1} - 1}{2} \right) \equiv 4 \pmod{5};$$

$$\text{pod}_5 \left(\frac{p^{4k+2} - 1}{2} \right) \equiv 3 \pmod{5}$$

and

$$\text{pod}_5 \left(\frac{p^{4k+3} - 1}{2} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{5};$$

if $p \equiv 4 \pmod{5}$, then

$$\text{pod}_5 \left(\frac{p^{2k} - 1}{2} \right) \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$$

and

$$\text{pod}_5 \left(\frac{p^{2k+1} - 1}{2} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{5};$$

if $p \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, then

$$\text{pod}_5 \left(\frac{p^k - 1}{2} \right) \equiv 1 \pmod{5}.$$

Theorem 3. For any $k \geq 0$, let p be an odd prime. Then we have the following:

(i) if $p \equiv 1 \pmod{7}$, then

$$\text{pod}_7 \left(\frac{3(p^{2k} - 1)}{4} \right) \equiv 2k + 1 \pmod{7};$$

(ii) if $p \equiv 2, 5 \pmod{7}$, then

$$\text{pod}_7 \left(\frac{3(p^{6k} - 1)}{4} \right) \equiv 1 \pmod{7};$$

$$\text{pod}_7 \left(\frac{3(p^{6k+4} - 1)}{4} \right) \equiv 5 \pmod{7}$$

and

$$\text{pod}_7 \left(\frac{3(p^{6k+2} - 1)}{4} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{7};$$

(iii) if $p \equiv 3, 4, 6 \pmod{7}$, then

$$\text{pod}_7 \left(\frac{3(p^{6k} - 1)}{4} \right) \equiv 1 \pmod{7};$$

$$\text{pod}_7 \left(\frac{3(p^{6k+4} - 1)}{4} \right) \equiv 3 \pmod{7}$$

and

$$\text{pod}_7 \left(\frac{3(p^{6k+2} - 1)}{4} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{7};$$

(iv) if $p \equiv 0 \pmod{7}$, then

$$\text{pod}_7 \left(\frac{3(p^{2k} - 1)}{4} \right) \equiv 1 \pmod{7}.$$

Theorem 4. For any $k \geq 0$, let p be an odd prime. Then we have the following:

(i) if $p \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$, then

$$\text{pod}_{25}(5p^k - 3) \equiv k + 1 \pmod{5};$$

(ii) if $p \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$, then

$$\text{pod}_{25}(5p^{4k} - 3) \equiv 1 \pmod{5};$$

$$\text{pod}_{25}(5p^{4k+1} - 3) \equiv 4 \pmod{5};$$

$$\text{pod}_{25}(5p^{4k+2} - 3) \equiv 3 \pmod{5}$$

and

$$\text{pod}_{25}(5p^{4k+3} - 3) \equiv 0 \pmod{5};$$

(iii) if $p \equiv 3 \pmod{5}$, then

$$\text{pod}_{25}(5p^{4k} - 3) \equiv 1 \pmod{5};$$

$$\text{pod}_{25}(5p^{4k+1} - 3) \equiv 3 \pmod{5};$$

$$\text{pod}_{25}(5p^{4k+2} - 3) \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$$

and

$$\text{pod}_{25}(5p^{4k+3} - 3) \equiv 0 \pmod{5};$$

(iv) if $p \equiv 4 \pmod{5}$, then

$$\text{pod}_{25}(5p^{2k} - 3) \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$$

and

$$\text{pod}_{25}(5p^{2k+1} - 3) \equiv 0 \pmod{5};$$

(v) if $p \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, then

$$\text{pod}_{25}(5p^k - 3) \equiv 1 \pmod{5}.$$

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